

SCIENTIFIC REPORT

Care4food

CARE4FOOD: CHOICES AND PERCEPTIONS
OF FOOD SECURITY AND SUSTAINABILITY
IN A CLIMATE CHANGE CONTEXT IN
PORTUGAL.

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CARE4FOOD

Choices and perceptions of food security and sustainability in a climate change context

Escolhas e perceções de segurança alimentar e sustentabilidade num contexto de alterações climáticas em Portugal.

Technical report

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ABBREVIATIONS

AMP Área Metropolitana do Porto

AML Área Metropolitana de Lisboa

BMI Body Mass Index

CATI Computer-Assisted Telephone Interviewing

COM-B Capability, Opportunity, Motivation – Behaviour model

EU European Union

FAO Food and Agriculture Organization (of the United Nations)

FIES Food Insecurity Experience Scale

GDP Gross Domestic Product

GHG Greenhouse Gas (Emissions)

GIS / ArcGIS Geographic Information System / ArcGIS Pro

INE Instituto Nacional de Estatística (Portugal)

NUTS Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics

SDGs Sustainable Development Goals

SEM Socio-Ecological Model

SPSS Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

WHO World Health Organization

SUMMARY

The Care4Food study investigates food choices and perceptions related to food security and sustainability within the context of climate change in mainland Portugal. Using a combined socio-ecological (SEM) and behavioral (COM-B) framework, the study analyzes both individual-level behaviors and regional dynamics.

It draws from a comprehensive survey of 1,813 respondents, alongside secondary data such as land use and regional statistics

The study surveyed 1,813 individuals representing households, with a balanced gender distribution and an average respondent age of 50. Most households consist of two members, and 10% of participants were born outside Portugal. While 75% report no chronic illness, 62% of respondents are overweight or obese. Households with children spend less on food, likely due to prioritizing other expenses, and higher education levels are most prevalent in Grande Lisboa.

13% of households experience moderate to severe food insecurity, with the Algarve being most affected. Over 60% of respondents are overweight or obese, despite most believing they follow healthy diets, highlighting a clear gap between perception and behavior. A sustainable diet score was developed to address this misalignment. The score reveals that 75% of the sample has less healthy and sustainable practices which may lead to high health and environmental costs.

Barriers to healthier eating include food cost, time constraints, and lack of knowledge. Public support is strong for policies that promote healthy and sustainable food systems, though taxation on meat remains unpopular. Women and older individuals are more likely to adopt sustainable practices.

Findings also reveal significant territorial disparities, particularly between urbanized coastal areas and aging, low-density inland regions. Regions like Algarve and Alentejo Litoral stand out for their agricultural, touristic, and multicultural characteristics, while rural-urban transition zones show emerging accessibility issues, often car-dependent. This shows that policies should be better tailored to the local context, together with consumers, producers, policy-makers, land use planners, and nutrition experts.

Overall, Care4Food underscores the need for systemic change that aligns food policy with health, equity, and environmental sustainability. The report advocates targeted policy interventions, integration of agroecology, and the creation of a Food Sustainability Observatory to support monitoring and civic engagement at local levels. A Geographic information system dashboard is complementary to this report as a way of feeding and replicate food scores at a more administrative level (feeding municipalities public policies).

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Food security and food sustainability

Global food systems—including production, transportation, processing, packaging, storage, retail, consumption, and food loss and waste—are both significantly contributing to and being affected by climate change. This dynamic threatens to undermine food security, defined as the condition in which “all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life” (FAO, 2019). This definition encompasses key dimensions: availability, accessibility, and utilization—in terms of both safety and nutritional value—as well as sociocultural acceptability and, critically, the stability of these conditions over time.

While food is impacted by extreme events like floods or drought, causing food shortages and food insecurity (Ritchie (2024), food and intensive agriculture are also one of the main contributors to climate change, particularly through greenhouse gas emissions. According to Crippa, M. (2021) a third of GHG emissions comes from the agricultural sector. Animal-based foods, particularly red meat, dairy, and farmed shrimp, have the highest GHG emissions due to deforestation for grazing land, methane emissions from livestock digestion, nitrous oxide from animal waste and fertilizers, or the destruction of carbon-absorbing mangrove forests for shrimp farming. In contrast, plant-based foods, such as fruits, vegetables, whole grains, legumes, and nuts require less energy, land, and water, making them more environmentally sustainable (Babiker et al., 2022). Figure 1 shows the GHG emissions per kilogram of food protein, with beef, followed by lamb and shellfish as highest contributors (Poore & Nemecek, 2018).

Data source: Poore and Nemecek (2018)

OurWorldinData.org/environmental-impacts-of-food | CC BY

Figure 1 - Greenhouse gas emissions per 100 grams of protein.

Source: Poore, J., & Nemecek, T. (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science*. Processed by Our World in Data [retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/ghg-per-protein-poore> on March 2025]

On another angle, the huge consumption of meals containing high calories, meat protein, and dairy not only contributes to greenhouse gas emissions but also to the risk of disease (Willett, et

al. 2019). The number of calories that a healthy adult should eat is on average 2000 to 2500 calories. However, this value has been growing to around 3500 in Europe and a little bit more in Northern America (FAO, 2023).

Traditional food systems are negatively impacting various dimensions of food security and sustainability. They have shown unable to provide quality food and to give equitable access also in terms of culturally appropriate food, and to preserve the environment (Bene et al. 2019). Secure food systems must be productive, deliver healthy and nutritious diets, be environmentally sustainable to address climate change, and be inclusive and just to support the most vulnerable populations (Viana et al., 2020).

The following diagram (Figure 2) from Berry et al. (2015) highlights how sustainability can be integrated in food security, by rethinking food availability in terms of agri-environmental concerns, accessibility by integrating the economic access to the physical one, and utilization by favouring a good nutrition that is socio-culturally accepted.

Figure 2: interrelations between food security and sustainability.

Source: Berry, E. et al (2015).

What is a sustainable diet?

In 2019, the EAT-Lancet Commission introduced the first scientific targets for healthy and sustainable diets—known as the Planetary Health Diet. This framework established daily intake ranges for each food group, while allowing flexibility to adapt to local and individual contexts. According to the Commission, global adoption of this diet could deliver significant health benefits while preserving biodiversity and protecting ecosystems for current and future generations (Willett, 2019). The report firmly positioned sustainability and health as dual objectives within the food system.

The EAT diet emphasizes increasing the intake of plant-based foods—particularly legumes, fruits, and vegetables—with a recommended minimum of 400 grams of fruits and vegetables per day. This aligns with growing scientific evidence supporting the health advantages of plant-based diets (Rizzo et al., 2013). At the same time, the diet advises reducing animal protein consumption to

approximately two eggs (13 grams of protein daily), 98 grams of red meat, 203 grams of poultry, and 196 grams of fish per week (WHO, 2021). It also encourages prioritizing locally produced foods to minimize food miles.

However, even when accounting for transport emissions, imported plant-based proteins generally have a lower environmental impact than animal proteins. Studies by Mohammadi et al. (2024) and Rizzo et al. (2013) confirm that plant-based diets have smaller carbon footprints. For instance, while tofu may involve long-distance transportation, its overall environmental cost remains significantly lower than that of beef. Red meat has been shown to have a disproportionately high impact in terms of water and land use compared to plant-based alternatives (Mekonnen & Hoekstra, 2012). Moreover, research suggests that healthy and sustainable diets may be more affordable than animal protein-rich diets, especially in upper-middle- to high-income countries (Springmann et al., 2021).

In line with the FAO (2019) and the EAT-Lancet Commission (2019), this study adopts both sustainability and nutrition as intrinsically linked components of the same concept. A sustainable diet is one that not only has low environmental impact but also promotes health and well-being.

Yet the fundamental question remains: ***Can everyone achieve food security while also adopting a sustainable diet?***

Access to sustainable and nutritious food remains a significant challenge for vulnerable populations even in developed countries. In Europe, food insecurity affects between 9,5 % of the general population, with higher rates observed among migrants, women, children, older adults, single-parent households, people with unstable incomes and living in food deserts, while people at risk of poverty at the EU level was 22.3%, (Eurostat, 2023). In Portugal, 4% of the population has faced moderate to severe food insecurity in 2024 (INE, *Inquérito às condições de vida e rendimento*, 2024).

A recent study in Portugal highlights that single households, basic education levels, immigrants, and low-income families with children, were more likely to belong to food insecure households and to have an unhealthy diet (Costa et al., 2024). This typology of households is frequently present in disadvantaged neighbourhoods often facing limited availability of affordable, healthy food options. Factors such as living in “food deserts” where access to fresh produce is scarce exacerbate the difficulty in maintaining a healthy diet (Briazu et al. 2024).

More broadly, the declining adherence to Mediterranean dietary habits among Portuguese households has led to a reduction in overall diet quality. This trend is particularly evident among food-insecure populations, who not only exhibit lower adherence to the Mediterranean diet but also face higher rates of non-communicable diseases, a diminished quality of life, and greater reliance on healthcare resources (Gregório et al., 2018). When we consider these dietary trends alongside specific challenges, such as climate change (e.g., water scarcity) (Galli et al., 2020), agricultural soil sealing (Abrantes et al., 2016, 2023), limited food and nutrition literacy, and the widespread misinformation and disinformation on social media, the urgency of strengthening policies that promote sustainable diets becomes clear. These policies must also ensure social equity in access to nutritious food (Capone et al., 2021), not only for disadvantaged groups but for society (Silva et al., 2023).

This raises another important question: ***Is it possible to achieve a secure and sustainable diet under the current combination of internal and external pressures?***

1.2. Socio-ecological framework applied to food analysis

People-centric frameworks, such as the *Socio-Ecological Model (SEM)* and the *Behaviour Change Wheel* (Capability, Opportunity, Motivation Behaviour – COM-B), are increasingly being integrated into food security and sustainability strategies. These models place individuals—and their resources—at the center of dynamic interactions with both society and nature.

Story et al. (2008) adapted McLeroy et al.'s (1988) SEM, proposing five levels of influence: individual, interpersonal, organizational, community, and policy. The model sought to better understand the complexity of eating behaviors and food choices by highlighting the multilevel linkages and interactions that shape health and nutrition outcomes. The SEM offers a comprehensive framework for analyzing the interplay between personal food choices, cultural and economic drivers, and broader goals of environmental sustainability (Story et al., 2008).

Focusing specifically on the individual level, behavior change toward healthier and more sustainable eating patterns is shaped by a complex interplay of factors, as outlined in the COM-B model (Michie et al., 2011; Salmon et al., 2020):

1. Motivation – Whether individuals *value* the behavior, shaped by beliefs, emotions, and personal relevance. For example, individuals may be more motivated to change if they associate dietary choices with environmental impact or personal well-being.
2. Capability – Whether individuals *can* make the behavior change, which includes both physical and psychological factors such as age, gender, education, skills, and nutritional literacy. Awareness of the environmental impact of diets, for instance, can influence decisions to adopt plant-based eating patterns, reduce meat intake, or minimize food waste.
3. Opportunity – Whether the *external environment* enables or constrains behavior change. This includes access to healthy foods, affordability, social support, and policy environments. Perceived barriers—such as food deserts, cultural norms, or pricing—can either hinder or enable sustainable food choices

Together, the SEM and COM-B frameworks highlight the need to consider both individual agency and structural conditions when promoting dietary shifts. By doing so, it is possible to better design interventions that support healthier and more sustainable behaviors within real-world contexts (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Social ecological model of behaviour change and the Capability, Motivation and Opportunity behavior (COM-B).
Source: Michie, et al. (2011).

As an example, for consumers to adopt climate-friendly food choices, they must first believe that their individual actions can positively impact the environment. However, research indicates that a lack of belief in the connection between food choices and climate change, combined with deeply ingrained eating habits, often prevents many individuals from making more sustainable decisions. Notably, women tend to be more convinced than men of the environmental benefits of dietary changes (Mäkiniemi & Vainio, 2014; Tobler et al., 2011a).

On the other hand, health-related motivations are often more immediate and personally relevant triggers for behavior change. These motivations can indirectly facilitate more sustainable eating patterns, particularly when they involve reducing the consumption of animal-based products. In such cases, sustainable choices—like opting for seasonal and locally produced foods—can offer dual benefits: improving personal health while also supporting environmental goals. Nonetheless, food choices remain influenced by a range of individual factors, including taste preferences, which can act as either a barrier or enabler to dietary change (Siegrist et al., 2015).

These internal factors are further shaped and influenced by external layers of behavior, as outlined in the socio-ecological model—specifically at the interpersonal (micro), organizational/community (meso), and policy (macro) levels. For instance, social norms, particularly those surrounding meat consumption, continue to present a significant barrier to dietary shifts, as highlighted by Springmann et al. (2018). Even when individuals are motivated and capable of change, these norms can reinforce unsustainable eating patterns.

In addition, affordability and infrastructure limitations, especially in lower-income communities, often restrict access to sustainable food options, making large-scale adoption more difficult. At a broader level, factors such as food marketing, agricultural policies, and the economic structures that influence food pricing play a major role in shaping consumer behavior and dietary patterns (Story et al., 2008). These macro-level influences can either support or undermine efforts to promote healthier and more sustainable diets, depending on how they are designed and implemented (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Socio ecological model (SEM) of food behavior.

Source: Story et al (2008)

The FAO Food Wheel (2018) serves as a visual representation that exemplifies how the principles of the Socio-Ecological Model (SEM) can support a more holistic understanding of food security and sustainability. It underscores the idea that human behavior is complex and multidimensional, shaped not only by individuals’ inherent characteristics—such as knowledge, preferences, and health status—but also by the broader contexts in which they live. These contexts span from local to global scales and encompass both natural systems (e.g., ecosystems, climate, biodiversity) and social systems (e.g., culture, economy, governance). By integrating these dimensions, the FAO Food Wheel illustrates how SEM characteristics can be applied to address the interconnected factors influencing food-related behaviors and outcomes.

Figure 5: FAO’s holistic Food wheel including a SEM and COM-B perspective.

Source: FAO, 2018

This study aligns with the Lisbon Regional Strategy 2030, particularly with its second priority axis, focused on environmental and food sustainability and the mitigation of natural risks. It is also consistent with the Regional Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3 Lisboa), especially in the areas of agri-food and the blue economy. with the EAT-AML strategy, particularly in axes 3, 5, and 6. At the European levels, the study is in line with several key policy frameworks, including: the Farm to Fork Strategy and the EU Biodiversity Strategy, both under the umbrella of the European Green Deal, The Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (2015-2025), or the Glasgow Declaration on Food and Climate (2020).

1.3. Aim of the study

The Care4Food study seeks to generate territorial knowledge about individuals' food choices and perceptions in relation to food security and sustainability. Dietary practices are examined through a dual lens: adequate nutrition and environmental preservation, particularly in the context of climate change. In other words, the project aims to explore how individuals perceive food security and how their dietary choices align with or diverge from sustainability goals—while also assessing the influence of geography and the local food environment on these choices.

To do this, the study views the food system through the Socio-Ecological Model (SEM) of behavioral change, focusing on the dynamic interactions between individuals and their social and environmental contexts, and how these interactions can shape behaviors toward more sustainable and secure food practices. It raises critical questions: *How can we build a sustainable food system that works for everyone while protecting the climate? What multilevel factors—from individual characteristics to broader social and environmental conditions—shape food choices and the potential for positive dietary transitions?*

Care4Food adopts a multilevel framework, combining SEM with the COM-B model (Capability, Opportunity, Motivation – Behaviour), explicitly incorporating spatial and temporal dimensions—that is, how behaviors and environments adapt and evolve over time. The study aims to understand Portuguese food habits towards a sustainability and regional patterns as well as identify both barriers and enablers of behavioral change in support of more sustainable food systems (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: framework adopted from Mitchel etl. 2011 to analyse behavioural changes toward food security and sustainability

The Care4Food study follows a three-step methodology to explore the relationship between individual food choices, sustainability, and territorial context.

1. Regional Food System Analysis: In the first step, after literature review, we collect and analyze which key regional indicators of the mainland Portugal better reflect a food system analysis. This analysis is based on indirect data, including census statistics and land use/land cover maps, to understand how structural and geographic factors shape the food environment (NUTS III are represented). Food security dimensions of availability and accessibility are analyzed here, for instance through indicators such as food deserts or fresh veg&fruits accessibility ¹

¹ Food Desert Methodology

The analysis was based on COS 1.1 and 1.2, combined with a 500-meter buffer around fresh food markets, using spatial overlay to extract urban areas located outside these buffer zones.

Example – Barrancos: Total urban area: 660,000 m²; Urban area outside a 500-meter radius of a market: 77,500 m²; Resulting percentage classified as a food desert: 11.74%.

To estimate how much population resides in these areas, BGRl and subsection data were used, considering the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP). Population proportions were estimated based on the area of each subsection that falls inside and outside the buffer. Results: Total population by subsection: 9,855,909; Population intersecting the 500-meter buffer: 6,908,689; Estimated population in urban food desert areas: 3,183,274 (i.e., living more than 500 meters from a fresh food outlet)

In addition to this calculation, further analyses were conducted: The fresh-to-bad food ratio, The percentage of "bad food" outlets near schools (by municipality). The percentage of urban area classified as food desert

2. **Population Survey:** The second step involves a direct survey of the mainland Portuguese population to gain insights into daily food choices and perceptions of sustainable diets. The focus is on two dimensions of food security: accessibility and utilization. The survey explores how people make decisions about what to eat, their awareness of environmental impacts, and how they perceive the sustainability of their diets. A Food score is built under certain responses.
3. **Exploratory quantitative analysis:** In the final step, a quantitative model—combining statistical analysis and machine learning techniques—is applied to identify key drivers of behavioral change. This model integrates individual-level factors and environmental/contextual patterns to better understand the complex dynamics influencing food-related behaviors.

The results are synthesized and shared through a dashboard and a story map, designed to facilitate public understanding and support broader dissemination to both scientific and non-scientific audiences (Figure 7).

Figure 7 – Workflow of the care4food study
(Image generated from chatGPT, 2025)

The Care4Food study aligns with Sustainable Development Goals 2 (Zero Hunger), 10 (Reduced Inequalities), and 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), as well as the European Union’s Farm to Fork Strategy, by promoting equitable access to sustainable and healthy diets while addressing regional disparities and supporting the transformation of food systems at the territorial level.

2. DATA AND METHODS

2.1. Case study presentation

The study overviews Portugal Mainland referring to the continental part of the Portuguese Republic, excluding the autonomous regions of the Azores and Madeira². It is bordered by Spain to the east and north, and the Atlantic Ocean to the west and south.

In terms of administrative and statistical divisions, Portugal follows the European Union's Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) system. This system is used for regional statistics, economic analysis, and European funding allocation. The NUTS system is divided into three levels:

- NUTS I: this includes Mainland Portugal, Azores, and Madeira;
- NUTS II: it comprises seven regions on the mainland (Norte, Centro, Grande Lisboa, Península de Setúbal, Oeste e Vale do Tejo, Alentejo, Algarve) and the two island regions.
- NUTS III: these are subregions within the NUTS II areas, offering a more detailed level of regional analysis. Mainland Portugal is divided into 26 NUTS III subregions, and these will be used for the aggregated analysis³. The following table highlights their total population, gender and age distribution, and GDP per capita, in 2023.

All regions exhibit a slightly higher female population percentage, consistent with national trends. Regarding GDP, the AML, particularly Grande Lisboa, stands out with the highest value, reflecting its status as the country's economic hub. Other regions like Algarve and Alentejo Litoral also show relatively high GDP per capita, indicative of their economic activities (tourism and agriculture).

Table 1 - Main indicators of the studied regions

NUTS III Region	Total Population	Female Population (%)	GDP per Capita (€)	Age 0-14 (%)	Age 65+ (%)
<i>Norte</i>					
Alto Minho	234 215	52,6	63	11,0	32,3
Cávado	429 833	51,7	67,2	12,9	33,1
Ave	422 464	51,5	64,6	12,1	32,3
Área Metropolitana do Porto	1 802 664	52,4	76,7	12,4	35,0
Alto Tâmega	83 669	52,2	52,8	8,9	28,1
Tâmega e Sousa	409 348	51,5	50,5	12,2	30,5
Douro	184 195	52,2	60,5	10,2	24,1
Terras de Trás-os-Montes	107 473	51,9	59,4	9,5	24,0
<i>Centro</i>					
Região de Aveiro	384 689	51,9	77,6	12,5	34,0

² The Azores and Madeira regions were excluded from this analysis due to time and budget constraints. Their inclusion would require theoretical and methodological adjustments to account for their insular and peripheral characteristics, which differ significantly from the mainland context in terms of geography, food systems, and socio-economic dynamics.

³ Some variables of the INE are only available for the Área Metropolitana de Lisboa. That is the aggregation of Península de Setúbal and Grande Lisboa.

Região de Coimbra	446 982	52,5	69,9	11,3	31,0
Região de Leiria	297 222	51,7	75,8	12,4	30,5
Viseu Dão Lafões	256 810	52,4	61,8	11,3	29,1
Beira Baixa	81 694	52,1	65	10,4	28,0
Beiras e Serra da Estrela	209 896	52,3	55,1	9,7	25,7
Oeste e Vale do Tejo					
Oeste	388 396	51,6	59,8	13,0	32,6
Médio Tejo	234 765	52,3	62,2	11,3	28,9
Lezíria do Tejo	247 764	51,9	66,8	12,8	30,8
Grande Lisboa + Península de Setúbal (former NUTS II Área metropolitana de Lisboa)*					
Grande Lisboa + Península de Setúbal	2 961 177	52,8	127,3 + 54,4	14,5	36,4
Alentejo					
Alentejo Litoral	101 388	48,5	101	11,9	29,3
Baixo Alentejo	115 757	50,9	79,3	12,9	30,4
Alto Alentejo	104 081	52,4	60,9	11,8	29,4
Alentejo Central	153 475	51,9	67,9	12,2	31,0
Algarve					
Algarve	484 122	51,4	87	13,7	32,7

* This region is composed of Nuts 3 Península de setúbal and Nuts 3 grande lisboa, but for the purpose of this study where we aim to compare both metropolitan regions (Porto and Lisbon) we have aggregated the two subregions in one.
Source: INE, Estimativas da População, 2023

Figure 8: Mainland Portugal NUTSII and III
Source: DGT, SNIG, 2024

2.2. Data collection

The data acquisition process combines both direct and indirect methods. Direct data is collected through a survey conducted by GfK, which provides insights into individual behaviors and perceptions regarding food security and sustainability. Indirect data is gathered from sources such as the National Institute of Statistics, OpenStreetMap, and the National Geographic Information System (SNIG), particularly for land use and land cover information. While the survey data captures individual-level decision-making, the statistical and spatial data help contextualize those behaviors within broader environmental and socio-economic settings.

All collected data are systematically organized and stored in a spatial database, both at the individual level and aggregated at the NUTSIII regional level ensuring a structured foundation for integrated analysis (*will be available in Arcgis online, Zenodo and University of Lisbon repository*). A dashboard for visualization and interactive analysis can be found at Available at <https://www.arcgis.com/apps/dashboards/9088fa801b454f32afa39d5c84e10c7b>

2.2.1. Sample and survey structure

The universe of the survey, conducted by GfK for the Care4Food project, consisted of individuals representing their household, of both genders, aged 18 and older, residing in mainland Portugal.

Data collection was carried out through telephone interviews, using the CATI (Computer-Assisted Telephone Interviewing) system, between July 8 and August 24, 2024. Interviews were conducted between 5 PM and 10 PM on weekdays and between 11 AM and 10 PM on weekends.

Respondents were selected using the quota sampling method, based on a matrix that cross-referenced Gender, Age (4 groups: 18 to 24, 24 to 44, 45 to 64 and 65 and more), and Region. There are 8 regions comprising the Norte, where the Metropolitan Area of Porto was separated from it because of its urban characteristics; the other regions are Centro, Oeste e Vale do Tejo, Grande Lisboa e Peninsula de Setubal (both forming the Metropolitan area of Lisbon, Alentejo and Algarve). These Regions (NUTSII) served as the starting point for selecting households through the random generation of fixed and mobile phone numbers, following the prefixes of each region and operator, while applying the quotas (table 1 and 2). The final sample comprised 1,813 valid interviews, with an acceptable margin of error of 2% within a 95% confidence interval.

Table 2 - Sample size by region and gender

Region	Man	Woman	Non-binary	NR	Sample
Norte	154	167	2		323
Área Metropolitana do Porto (AMP)	154	172			326
Centro	148	160			308
Grande Lisboa	170	197	3		370
Oeste e Vale do Tejo	71	83		1	155
Península de Setúbal	69	82			151
Alentejo	44	47			91
Algarve	41	48			89
Sample	851	956	5	1	1813

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

Table 3 – Sample size by region and gender

Region	18-24 years	25-44 years	45-64 years	65 >=
Norte	8%	30%	36%	25%
Área Metropolitana do Porto	8%	30%	36%	26%
Centro	7%	27%	35%	31%
Oeste e Vale do Tejo	7%	28%	34%	30%
Grande Lisboa	9%	33%	32%	26%
Península de Setúbal	9%	30%	32%	28%
Alentejo	4%	25%	36%	34%
Algarve	4%	29%	37%	29%
Total	8%	30%	35%	28%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

The survey started after agreeing on the informed consent about the study and it had 35 questions, and it has the following structure: individual and household⁴ socio-economic, demographic, and health situation characterization; its food security, focusing on accessibility; dietary habits and practices; factors of changes in dietary behaviour toward sustainability and healthy food choices; perceptions of policy measures and governmental responsibilities. Most part of the questions were closed responses with a nominal and ordinal scale.

The survey was built to address the factors that determine behaviour changes toward healthier and more sustainable food choices, namely Motivation, Capability and Opportunity. It also followed 3 questions of the the food insecurity experience scale (fies) of FAO (Ballard, 2013) and key questions adapted from the National Food, Nutrition and Physical Activity Survey of 2015-2016 (Lopes at al., 2018), as some comparison could be expected.

A pre-test was conducted with the objective of establishing a minimum threshold below which interviews would be considered low quality, evaluating question comprehension, identifying difficulties encountered by respondents, testing the CAPI script to validate inconsistencies between responses, and assessing the total duration of the interview which took about 15 to 18 minutes.

2.2. Proposing quantitative indicators

The survey has mostly nominal and ordinal questions, and for purposes of greater analytical power we have created some quantitative variables enabling a more robust statistical analysis of relations between variables, namely of food security, health and food scores.

⁴ Household composition referred to the number of people living in the same house, regardless of family relationships.

2.2.1. Food security indicator

Food security, or the perception of food security is analysed three questions adapted from the FAO - Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) (Ballard, et al. 2013): *Were you worried about not having enough food due to a lack of money or other means (e.g., lack of equipment, time, difficulty accessing the supermarket, etc.)? Were you unable to have a healthy and nutritious diet due to a lack of money or other means? Did you run out of food at home due to a lack of money or other means?* The scale ranges from 1 (food secure) to 4 (severe food insecurity).

As we only had 3 questions out of the 8 normally used by FAO, we propose a composite indicator based on 5 variables of the survey (having children, being unemployed, having a lower income, and expenses on food). According to literature review, there are some key factors that contributes to food insecurity related with socio-economic factors (Grimaccia & Naccarato, 2019). As variables were mostly nominal, Chi-square helped us to identify which variables were related with the FEIS scale. They were “having teenage children” (<0.01), “income” (<0.01), “food expenses” (<0.05), and “professional status” (<0.01). The composite indicator is a weighted mean of the variables and FEIS as follows:.)

Insecurity indicator

$$= (\text{children}_{17} * 0.15) + (\text{income} * 0.15) + (\text{profession} * 0.15) + (\text{FEIS} * 0.5)$$

The results are classified through an adaptation of the FIES scale < 0,5 - Food security; between 0,5 to 0,9 – marginal or potential food security; between 1 to 1,5 – Moderate insecurity and > 1,5 – severe insecurity

As we can see in table 4 both indicators are very close to each other, being security overestimated by the FEIS indicator in 7%. Otherwise, other values are close.

Table 4– Insecurity levels according to FEIS and Composite indicator

	FEIS indicator (FAO)		Composite indicator	
Security	1338	74%	1213	67%
Potential/marginal security	248	14%	309	17%
Moderate insecurity	143	8%	177	10%
Severe insecurity	84	5%	114	6%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

2.2.2. Body mass index

Self-reported weight and height in the survey were used to calculate the participants’ body mass index (BMI), classified according to the criteria of the World Health Organization (WHO, 2010)⁵

⁵ From WHO (2010) “A healthy lifestyle - WHO recommendations at <https://www.who.int/europe/news-room/fact-sheets/item/a-healthy-lifestyle---who-recommendations>” [retrieved on 28/03/2025]

Table 5– Nutritional status of the respondents according to WHO classification (in percentage)

BMI	Nutritional status	
Below 18.5	Underweight	1,66%
18.5–24.9	Normal weight	36,18%
25.0–29.9	Pre-obesity	49,74%
> 30.0	Obesity	12,42%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024, adapted from WHO, 2010

2.2.3. Food Sustainability

a) Indicator (food sustainability score)

To better understand perceptions of sustainable dietary habits and practices, our analysis focuses on responses to the question: “Do you consider that you follow a healthy and sustainable diet?”, using a Likert scale from 1 (*not at all healthy and sustainable*) to 5 (*very healthy and sustainable*). While this self-assessment provides insight into individual perceptions, it is important to acknowledge that such responses may be overestimated due to social desirability bias—individuals tend to report behaviors they perceive as socially acceptable or desirable (de Ridder et al., 2012). To address the gap between perceived and actual practices, we propose a *Food Sustainability Score*, constructed from the frequency of responses to a series of dietary and sustainable practices behavior questions. This allows for an objective comparison between perceived sustainability and actual reported habits.

- “Do you consider that you follow a healthy and sustainable diet...? 5 - Never; 4- Occasionally in the month; 3 - Once a week; 2 - A few times a week; 1 - Every day”;

- “How often do you consume each of the following foods...? 6 - Never; 5- Occasionally in the month; 4 - Once a week; 3 - A few times a week; 2- Every day; 1 - Several times a day. The groups of products are: White meat and fish; Red meat; Milk and dairy products; Eggs; Cereals, nuts, and legumes (includes bread, excludes ultra-processed breakfast cereals, for example); Vegetables; Fruits; Sweet and savoury snacks; cured meats and ultra-processed foods such as pre-cooked meals; Takeaway food.

- “How often do you have lunch and/or dinner outside home? 1 - Every day, 2 - A few times a week, 3 - Once a week, 4 - Occasionally in the month, 5 – Never”

- “How often do you buy fresh food products (i.e., fruit and vegetables)?: 1 - Every day, 2 - A few times a week, 3 - Once a week, 4 - Occasionally in the month, 5 – Never”

- What transport mode do you use? car, walking, other.

- Do you waste food? 1 - Every day, 2 - A few times a week, 3 - Once a week, 4 - Occasionally in the month, 5 – Never”

The final food score is calculated from **four sub-scores**:

1. **Protein Score (score_proteina)**
2. **Fruit and Vegetable Score (score_fruta)**
3. **Processed Foods Score (score_processados)**
4. **Sustainability Score (score_sustentabilidade)**

Each sub-score ranges from **1 (least sustainable)** to **5 (most sustainable)**. The **final score** is the arithmetic mean of the four sub-scores, i.e. a **composite score between 1 and 5**, representing the participant's general diet quality, considering **nutritional balance and sustainable behaviors (see box 1)**. This sustainable food score is aligned with academic research operationalizing sustainable diets through composite indices, namely, the Sustainable Diet Index (SDI) (Seconda et al., 2020) combining dietary quality, environmental footprint, economic cost, and socio-cultural practices; the Dietary Pattern Sustainability Index (DIPASI) (Bôto et al., 2024) measured deviation from the mediterranean diet as a reference sustainable pattern, or the Planetary Health Diet Index (PHDI) (Bui et al., 2024) quantified adherence to the EAT-Lancet diet, linking higher scores to reduced mortality and environmental impact.

Box 1

Sustainable food Scoring System - Formula Explanation

The set of formulas presented here compute a score based on questionnaire responses.

The calculation is structured into four sub-scores:

- Protein Score (score_proteina)
 - Fruit and Vegetable Score (score_fruta)
 - Processed Foods Score (score_processados)
 - Sustainability Score (score_sustentabilidade)
- Each sub-score ranges from 1 (least sustainable) to 5 (most sustainable).

The final score is the arithmetic mean of the four sub-scores.

1. Common Formula Structure

All scoring functions follow the same mathematical pattern:

$\text{number}(\min(5, \max(1, \text{base_score} + \text{adjustments})))$

The $\min(5, \dots)$ function ensures that no score exceeds 5.

The $\max(1, \dots)$ function ensures that the score does not fall below 1.

This guarantees that all sub-scores are normalized within the 1-5 range.

2. Protein Score (score_proteina)

Variables (questions) considered:

cereais - frequency of cereal consumption

carne_branca - white meat (fish/poultry)

carne_vermelha - red meat

leite - milk and dairy products

leguminosas - legumes (beans, lentils, etc.)

Scoring logic:

The protein score begins with a base value of 3, then applies several conditional adjustments:

Cereals and balanced protein sources: increased score if cereals are consumed daily or several times per week, combined with moderate consumption of white meat or dairy.

Red meat: low or occasional intake (nunca, ocasionalmente, 1x por semana) → +1

Moderate (algumas vezes por semana) → -2

Frequent or daily (1x por dia, várias vezes) → -3

White meat and dairy: Moderate weekly consumption increases the score; excessive or daily intake decreases it.

Legumes: Regular consumption (weekly or more) adds +1.

3. Fruit and Vegetable Score (score_fruta)

Variables considered:

frutas - fruit intake frequency

vegetais - vegetable intake frequency

Scoring logic

The score evaluates how regularly fruits and vegetables are consumed:

Frequency pattern Score

Both "várias vezes por dia" 5

Both daily or one daily and the other multiple times 4

Both several times per week 3

Both once per week 2

Less frequent consumption 1

An additional penalty (-1) is applied if one food group is consumed very frequently while the other is consumed rarely or never (to discourage imbalance).

4. Processed Foods Score (score_processados)

Variable considered:

snacks - frequency of processed snack consumption

Scoring logic

Frequency of consumption

Nunca (never) 5

Ocasionalmente no mês 4

Uma vez por semana 3

Algumas vezes por semana / Uma vez por dia 2

Várias vezes 1

This score inversely reflects the frequency of processed food intake: less frequent consumption yields a higher score.

5. Sustainability Score (score_sustentabilidade)

Model starts at 2 expecting more possible positive actions than negative ones

Variables considered:

take_away - frequency of take-away meals

jantar_fora - frequency of eating out

onde_compra - type of shop (e.g., supermarket, market, local producer)

como_desloca - mode of transport for food shopping

sobras - frequency of food waste

compra_frutas - frequency of purchasing fruit and vegetables

perto_longe - proximity preference when buying products and if it's part of the daily commuting

Scoring logic:

Rare or no take-away / eating out +1

Buying from local markets or producers +1

Using sustainable transport (walking/bicycle) +1

Using private car -2

```

Never wasting food      +1
Frequent food waste    -2
Buying fruit rarely    -1
Preferring nearby products  +1
Rarely choosing local options -1~

6. Final Score Calculation
The final diet quality score is computed as the mean of the four components:
(number({score_proteina}) +
number({score_fruta}) +
number({score_processados}) +
number({score_sustentabilidade})) / 4

```

b) Sustainable meal option

In the survey we ask people to choose a meal to prepare or to eat to analyse how much of this choice adheres to sustainable principles. This question also serves to validate other questions like frequency of eating certain products, type of diet and perceptions about healthy and sustainable diet.

The meals consider aspects like seasonality of the products, local and regional production, water usage, GHG emissions, organic production, and nutritional content (calories, protein, fat, and vitamins) thus combining both sustainable and nutritional aspects.

The proposed meals in the survey were built from three main international and national guidelines: the Lancet planetary plate, the Mediterranean diet food wheel of 2016 from the general directorate of health (Portugal) and the Prato Certo⁶. They were: Tofu Jardinière; Chickpeas with Poached Eggs; Goat and Vegetable Meatballs, Boiled Cod fish with Potatoes, Carrots, and Cabbage; Avocado, Mango from Algarve, and Shrimp Salad; and grilled Beef Steak with Rice and Salad.

The choices made by the participants were then ranked from 1 (worst option) to 3 (best option), as table 6 indicates.

Table 6– Nutritional and sustainability features of suggested meals

	Nutrition	Sustainability	Total score (Avg)
Tofu Jardinière	3/3 high protein, fiber, vitamins	2/3 not locally produced but plant-based	2.5/3 Best nutritious choice. Highly nutritious, but tofu import reduces sustainability
Chickpeas with Poached Eggs;	3/3 protein, fiber, iron, moderate fat	3/3 locally sourced, low impact	3/3 Best choice Locally sourced, high nutrition, sustainable
Goat meatballs and Vegetables	2/3 good protein, moderate fat	2/3 less sustainable than tofu/chickpeas	2/3

⁶ A platform created by the local organization In Loco Association, featuring recipes aligned with the principles of the Mediterranean Food Wheel, promoting healthy and sustainable eating (<https://www.pratocerto.pt/>)

Boiled Cod fish	2.5/3 omega-3, lean protein, veggies	1.5/3 fishing sustainability concerns	2/3
Avocado, Mango from Algarve, and Shrimp Salad	2/3 healthy fats, vitamins, high sugar	1/3 high water use, shrimp impact	1.5/3
Beef Steak with Rice and Salad	1.5/3 high protein, but high saturated fat	0.5/3 very high carbon footprint	1/3 Worst option High emissions, lower nutritional balance

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

2.3. Data analysis

The analysis of indicators was conducted using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28.0, ArcGIS Pro version 3.4, and Python (version 3).

SPSS was employed to assess associations between variables. For nominal variables, the chi-square test of independence was applied. For ordinal variables, relationships were examined using Spearman’s rank correlation and Cramér’s V, while Pearson’s correlation coefficient was used to evaluate associations between scale variables. Additionally, the Kruskal–Wallis H test, a non-parametric alternative to one-way ANOVA, was used to detect statistically significant differences across three or more independent groups. When significant differences were found, pairwise comparisons were carried out using the Mann–Whitney U test. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

A preliminary exploratory analysis revealed several strong chi-square associations. Variables such as gender, age, and professional status were significantly associated with the type of diet, frequency of consumption of specific food types, perceptions of a sustainable diet, and intentions or barriers to changing dietary habits. The presence or absence of reported diseases was associated with eating behaviors such as red meat and take-away consumption, as well as with preferences for local or organic food. Moreover, having children was associated with take-away consumption and the use of a car for grocery shopping. Other associations were identified between geographical location, shopping profiles, and dietary diversity.

Both SPSS and ArcGIS Pro were also used to characterize territorial types through multivariate statistical methods, such as k-means clustering.

Python (version 3) was used to conduct advanced statistical analysis, including the application of machine learning algorithms—such as logistic regression and random forest—for predictive modeling. The goal was to identify key factors influencing changes in food choices. Potential predictors included: Responses to the question “Have you changed your food habits or are you considering changing them?” (categorized as 1- has changed, 0 - considers change, 0 - has not changed).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Household characterisation

The study surveyed 1,813 individuals, each representing a household. Of these, 47% were men and 53% were women. The average age of respondents was 50 years, influenced by the minimum participation age of 18 (see Tables 7 and 8).

Approximately 10% of participants were born outside of Portugal, representing 17 different nationalities: Angola, Brazil, Cabo Verde, Congo, France, Equatorial Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, India, Luxembourg, Morocco, Mozambique, Russia, South Africa, Switzerland, Ukraine, and Venezuela. Most households were composed of two members (54%), followed by households with three or more members (28%). Individuals living alone accounted for 19% of the households.

Table 7– Number and percentage of adults per household

Household / region	Adults over 18-year-old					
	1 adult		2 adults		3 or more adults	
Norte	45	14%	167	52%	111	34%
AMP	58	18%	175	54%	93	29%
Centro	61	20%	163	53%	84	27%
Oeste e Vale do Tejo	26	17%	89	57%	40	26%
Grande Lisboa	89	24%	188	51%	93	25%
P. de Setúbal	29	19%	93	62%	29	19%
Alentejo	13	14%	47	52%	31	34%
Algarve	18	20%	51	57%	20	22%
Portugal (mainland)	339	19%	973	54%	501	28%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

Table 8– Percentage of adults and children by household

Household / region	Without children		12 to 17 years old				<12 years old			
			1 child		2 or more		1 child		2 or more	
Norte	213	66%	37	11%	7	2%	52	16%	27	8%
AMP	236	72%	31	10%	4	1%	43	13%	25	8%
Centro	216	70%	35	11%	3	1%	50	16%	23	7%
Oeste e Vale do Tejo	118	76%	17	11%	0	0%	13	8%	12	8%
Grande Lisboa (AML)	275	74%	40	11%	7	2%	56	15%	14	4%
P. de Setúbal (AML)	114	75%	14	9%	2	1%	23	15%	7	5%
Alentejo	61	67%	8	9%	1	1%	18	20%	6	7%
Algarve	60	67%	14	16%	2	2%	14	16%	5	6%
Portugal (mainland)	1293	71%	196	11%	26	1%	269	15%	119	7%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

6% of households consist of one adult and one child, while 1,293 households have no children. Additionally, 22% of households include children under the age of 12, most commonly one child (15%). This proportion is higher in the Alentejo region. The Algarve has the highest percentage of households with children aged 12 to 17, at 18%, compared to the national average of 12%.

Most household representatives have completed at least secondary education, with a significant number holding higher education degrees. This is especially notable in Grande Lisboa, where 58% have a higher education qualification. In contrast, the proportion of individuals with only primary education (completed or not) is higher in the Oeste and Vale do Tejo region (Figure 9).

Figure 9: level of education of the household representative
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

Regarding employment status, the majority of heads of households are either employed (64%) or retired (26%). The highest unemployment rates are found in the Península de Setúbal (12%), followed by the Área Metropolitana do Porto (AMP) with 8% (Figure 10).

Figure 10: householder representative – professional status by region
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

When asked about their physical condition (e.g. BMI) and health status (such as the presence of chronic diseases), 75% (1,313 individuals) of the households that responded to both questions reported no chronic illness. In contrast, approximately 25% of individuals reported having at least one health condition. 333 respondents reported one chronic disease, and 101 reported two or more.

Most participants were overweight, categorized as pre-obese (869 individuals), while obesity was observed in 217 participants, making up 62% of the sample. There appears to be a slight association between higher BMI and the presence of chronic diseases ($p < 0.01$). However, it is important to note that other factors may play a more significant role in determining overall health status (table 9).

Table 9– Relation between the percentage of chronic diseases reported and the BMI

BMI	No condition reported	1 disease	2 or more	Total
Mild underweight	1,3%	0,2%	0,1%	1,7%
Normal weight	26,5%	7,7%	1,9%	36,2%
Overweight	39,7%	8,1%	1,9%	49,7%
Obesity (all classes)	7,6%	3,0%	1,8%	12,4%
Total	75,2%	19,1%	5,7%	100%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

When asked about food expenses households with children tend to spend less on food compared to households without children. This may indicate that the household expenses are directed more toward other needs rather than food. The highest food expenditures are observed in between 200 and over 500 euros, where the majority of higher expenses occur⁷ (table 10).

⁷ The cut-off values used for categorizing household food expenses were based on data from the National Institute of Statistics (INE) (https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_destaques&DESTAQUESdest_boui=598753444&DESTAQU)

Table 10– Expenses on food by household with children and without children

	Without children		With children		Total	
< 50 Euros	6	86%	1	14%	7	0%
50 to 99 Euros	17	94%	0	0%	18	1%
100 to 199 Euros	95	90%	11	10%	106	7%
200 to 299	233	78%	65	22%	298	20%
300 to 499	388	65%	211	35%	599	40%
> 500	313	65%	165	35%	478	32%
Total	1052	70%	453	30%	1506	100%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

3.2. Household food security

3.2.1. Food security indicator as a measure of economic accessibility

Key issues surrounding food security—such as the unequal distribution of food and, in particular, the need for both physical and financial access to nutritious, healthy, and environmentally sustainable food—remain among the most pressing challenges faced by both the Global North and the Global South (Viana et al., 2022). In Mainland Portugal the majority of participants (73%) are food secure, with the highest levels observed in the Centro and Área Metropolitana do Porto (AMP) regions (both at 76%). In contrast, 13% of participants face moderate to severe food insecurity, with the Algarve showing the highest rate (22%). Moderate food insecurity is particularly notable in both Oeste e Vale do Tejo (OVT) and the Algarve (11% in each) (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Food security composite indicator by region (%)

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

ESmodo=2) and on from DECO Proteste, which regularly calculates the average monthly expenditure per person. DECO Proteste monitors the evolution of prices for essential food items, analyzing the total cost of a shopping basket every week (<https://www.deco.proteste.pt/familia-consumo/supermercado/noticias/precos-estao-aumentar-alimentos>)

According to figure 12, women are more affected by food insecurity than men, with 19% of women experiencing moderate to severe food insecurity, compared to 13% of men with a chi-square association between food security status and gender of $p < 0.05$).

Figure 12: Food security composite indicator by gender(%)
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

3.2.2. Physical accessibility to food

Food access can be both economic and physical—including time-related factors. *Figure 13* illustrates the average travel time to access a store that sells fresh fruits and vegetables, which is 11 minutes for most part of the participants, with a standard deviation of 7 minutes. Most regions report travel times between 10 and 14 minutes. The Area Metropolitana do Porto (AMP) has the shortest average distance, while in Alentejo, the average travel time is above the national average.

Figure 13 - Participant representation by average distance to a fresh food store (%)
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

Most participants (68%) buy fresh fruits and vegetables near their homes, while 8% purchase them closer to their workplace, and 24% report buying in both locations. Most participants are satisfied with their access to fresh products within a 5-minute walk from home (69%), with a statistically significant association of $p < 0.01$.

Table 11– Diversity fresh vegetables and fruits supply within a 5 minute walking distance from home

	Is there a diversity of fresh food supply near home?		Are you satisfied with the diversity of fresh food supply directly from the producer?	
	No	Yes	No	Yes
Norte	34%	66%	19%	81%
Área Metropolitana do Porto	27%	73%	18%	82%
Centro	39%	61%	16%	84%
Oeste e Vale do Tejo	38%	62%	21%	79%
Grande Lisboa	26%	74%	24%	76%
Península de Setúbal	27%	73%	25%	75%
Alentejo	32%	68%	20%	80%
Algarve	27%	73%	24%	76%
Total	31%	69%	20%	80%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

Of the 1,795 participants who responded to the question about the modes of transport that they use to purchase fresh fruits and vegetables, some use multiple transport modes, while the majority (63%) reported using a private car, and 34% reported walking. The car use is significantly associated with the average distance to the store ($p < 0.01$). Table 14 shows that for short distances (within 5 minutes), participants are more likely to walk (37%) when compared to the private car use (32%).

Table 12– Mode of transport by distance time

	Soft mode	Public transport	Car	Total	Soft mode	Public transport	Car	Total
5 minutes	268	8	438	714	37%	10%	32%	33%
6 to 10	274	18	524	816	38%	23%	39%	38%
11 to 15	109	20	247	376	15%	26%	18%	17%
16 or more	74	31	150	255	10%	40%	11%	12%
	725	77	1359	2161				100%
	34%	4%	63%	100%				

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

Differences in the use of transports modes by region are statistically evident (<0.01), confirming that the transportation modes vary depending on the region in which people live. Some regions have a significantly higher proportion of people walking to acquire fresh food, while others rely less on walking.

The percentage-based heatmap shows where walking is most common and where it is less used. AML and AMP have higher values (42% and 35%) possibly meaning that urban areas with high accessibility may see more walking, while rural areas might depend on motorized transport. This can also show that in more urbanized regions, car use might be lower due to the availability of nearby stores, and that metropolitan regions may have better public transport infrastructure, leading to a higher percentage of residents using walking and transport mode.

Figure 14: Percentage of participants in the survey using each transport mode by region
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

There is a statistically significant relationship between walking and buying from local or small-circuit markets, while the use of a private car is strongly associated with global retail purchases ($p < 0.01$).

When asked about the type of stores where they purchase fresh products, 20% of participants reported buying within small circuits, including direct purchases from local producers and street markets. This percentage is slightly higher (21%) in the Norte, AML, and OVT regions, where local agricultural production is more common. There is also a statistically significant regional variation in small circuit purchasing behavior ($p < 0.05$). Most participants purchase fresh products from local supermarkets, followed by global retail chains. Notably, 102 individuals reported buying from all types of outlets, while 387 participants shop in both local supermarkets and small-circuit markets.

Table 13— types of stores to purchase fresh fruits and vegetables

	Small chains	Local Supermarket and grocery stores	National/ global supermarkets chains	All types	Local and Small circuits
Norte	25%	42%	27%	1%	4%
AMP	21%	43%	31%	1%	4%
Centro	21%	40%	25%	3%	11%
OVT	21%	29%	22%	6%	21%
Grande Lisboa (AML)	17%	43%	27%	3%	11%
P. Setúbal (AML)	14%	34%	22%	5%	24%
Alentejo	18%	40%	16%	5%	21%

Algarve	17%	31%	29%	6%	17%
Total	20%	39%	26%	3%	12%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

2.2.3. Food utilization: dietary habits and practices

Participants largely follow a protein-rich diet (66%), while 31% adhere to a Mediterranean diet, and only 3% identify a vegan or vegetarian. Although 81% of participants report following a healthy and sustainable diet either daily or several times a week, this percentage drops among those following protein-heavy (67%) and high-fat diets (55%), and is higher among those following Mediterranean (81%) and flexitarian diets (40%). The relation between both variables are statistically significant at $p < 0.01$.

Table 14 – Relation between the type of diet (b) and perception of a healthy and sustainable diet (a)

What type of diet do you consider you follow? (b)	Do you consider that you follow a healthy and sustainable diet...(a)					Total (b)
	Never	Occasionally in the month	Once a week	A few times a week	Every day	
Mainly based on meat, fish, milk, and dairy products	86%	83%	83%	67%	55%	66%
Mainly based on fruit, vegetables, fish, and olive oil as main fat (e.g. Mediterranean, Flexitarian)	13%	14%	16%	31%	40%	31%
Special diet	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%
Vegan & Vegetarian	1%	3%	1%	2%	5%	3%
Total (a)	5%	9%	5%	47%	34%	100%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

The regional distribution of diets follows a similar pattern across the country, with the majority of participants adhering to diets rich in fat, dairy, and protein. The Mediterranean and flexitarian diets are more prevalent in the Algarve (39%), while special diets—such as vegetarian, vegan, or other specific dietary patterns—are more common in metropolitan areas.

Figure 15: Type of diet by region, in percentage
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

To assess whether participants perceive a connection between their diet and healthy, sustainable habits, we correlated indicators of perceived healthy and sustainable diets with actual healthy and sustainable practices (i.e. food score). The Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.28 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a very weak positive relationship between the two variables. This suggests a slight gap between perceived and real sustainable habits. Participants generally believe they are quite sustainable (4/5), but their actual behaviors reflect only moderate sustainability (3/5). The data show reasonable consistency, but also highlight a perception–practice gap that could be addressed through education and behavioral reinforcement.

Table 15 – Statistical analysis between Food sustainability score and Healthy and sustainable perceptions

Indicators	Score	Perceptions
Mean	3	4,0
Median	3	4,0
Mode	3.25	4,0
Standard deviation	0,8	1,1
Curtosis	-0,6	0,9
Assimetry	0,1	-1,2
Pearson correlation = 0,24		

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

Additionally, we assessed whether there was an association between diet perception, type of diet, and the type of meal participants would choose for lunch or dinner. The results revealed a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.01$).

In terms of dietary habits, most participants (66% or 1,175 individuals) follow a diet rich in fat, protein, and dairy, with 62% of those selecting meat and fish-based dishes. Approximately 38% of participants tend to choose less sustainable and less nutritious options, often favoring meat-based meals—though some of these choices may be influenced by perceived health benefits of salads or grilled items, without considering the full nutritional context of the dish. Meanwhile, 40% of participants prefer moderately sustainable and healthy options, with codfish emerging as the most frequently chosen dish. This reflects strong cultural food preferences, as codfish is common across all diet types. Notably, some individuals identifying as vegetarian or vegan selected animal-based dishes, which may indicate a gap in diet literacy—with 18 out of 48 respondents in these groups making such choices. Interestingly, only 22% of participants opted for healthier and more sustainable meal options.

Table 16— type of diet and preferred meal to eat or cook

	Meat, fish, milk, and dairy products	Fruit, vegetables, fish, and olive oil as the main fat	Special diet	Vegan & Vegetarian	Total
Avocado, Algarve mango, and shrimp salad (1)	15%	22%	0%	13%	17%
Grilled beef steak, rice, and salad (1)	26%	11%	40%	6%	21%
Goat meatballs with seasonal vegetables (2)	3%	2%	0%	2%	3%
Boiled codfish with potato and vegetables (2)	36%	41%	60%	17%	37%
Chickpeas with poached eggs (3)	16%	18%	0%	21%	17%
Tofu jardinière (3)	3%	6%	0%	42%	5%
Total	66%	31%	0%	3%	100%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

Figure 16 highlights an almost inverse relationship between dietary perceptions and actual meal choices, suggesting that individuals may place more importance on their perception of eating healthily than on the reality of their dietary behavior.

Figure 16:relation between the perception of a sustainable and healthy diet and meal option⁸
 Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

2.2.3.1. Gender and age in food utilization

The gender dimension, illustrated in Figure 17, shows that women are more likely to engage in healthier and more sustainable practices (77% compared to 23% of men). Conversely, men are more likely to adopt less healthy practices (57% compared to 43% of women). However, these differences are not statistically significant.

⁸ Classification: perception < 3 less healthy and sustainable practices; 3 to 4 moderate Healthy and sustainable practices and > 4 healthy and sustainable practices. Meal: less healthy and sustainable: Avocado, Algarve mango, and shrimp salad (1), Grilled beef steak, rice, and salad (1); moderate healthy and sustainable: Goat meatballs with seasonal vegetables (2) Boiled codfish with potato and vegetables (2) Healthy and sustainable: Chickpeas with poached eggs (3), Tofu jardinière (3)

Figure 17: relation between practices (food score) and perception of a sustainable diet
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

Although the majority of participants have healthy practices (47%), individuals aged 45 and older tend to follow a healthier and more sustainable diet compared to younger age groups. This association with age is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

Table 17– Sustainable food score by age

	18-24	25-44	45-64	65 and +	Total
Less healthy and sustainable practices	9%	35%	31%	25%	47%
Some Healthy and sustainable practices	7%	26%	38%	28%	42%
Healthy and sustainable practices	4%	21%	36%	39%	11%
Total	8%	31%	37%	30%	1813

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024.

The distribution of cooking responsibilities within households is uneven between men and women ($p < 0.01$). 70% of women report being primarily responsible for cooking, compared to 32% of men. Meanwhile, 27% of men state that they share the task with another household member, compared to 19% of women. Shared cooking responsibilities are more common among individuals aged 25 to 64, occurring in 73% of those cases.

Figure 18: distribution of cooking responsibilities by gender
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

3.3. Barriers and enabler of food change

When asked about making changes toward a healthier and more sustainable diet ("Have you already changed or would you consider changing your food choices to contribute to environmental sustainability?"), 32% (589 participants) reported that they have already changed their eating habits. 35% (635) said they have not made any changes, while the remaining 33% indicated they are considering making changes.

Figure 19: Changes made in eating habits
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

When asked what changes participants made, many reported making multiple changes (113 participants). The most common change was reducing red meat consumption (197 responses), followed by buying local and seasonal products or growing their own food, which together accounted for 170 responses. Regarding motivation for these changes, 321 responses cited health reasons, while 272 responses were driven by environmental sustainability concerns. Another

aspect explored among those who have changed or considered changing their diet is what they consider important to change. Overall, participants rated most aspects as very important, with the exception of buying alternative products and switching exclusively to a vegetarian or vegan diet, which received lower importance ratings (median scores of 1 and 2, respectively). This may reflect cultural influences that warrant further analysis (Figure 20).

Figure 20: What is important to change (responses from 1 - not important to 5 - very important)
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

Regarding barriers to dietary change (Figure 20), participants generally agreed that the price of food is a significant obstacle. Among those who have already changed their eating habits, additional barriers included the lack of clear food labeling and the belief that unhealthy food helps manage stress. Participants who are considering a change cited several barriers: high food prices, limited availability of fresh products, lack of time to cook, insufficient knowledge, and again, the perception that unhealthy food helps cope with stress. For those who are not planning to change, the main obstacles were food cost and lack of knowledge.

Figure 21: What is the main difficulty to changing habits (responses from 5 - not important to 1 -very important)
 Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

The Kruskal–Wallis H test was conducted to assess whether individuals' dietary change status— not changed, considering change, or has changed—is statistically related to their perceived difficulties in adopting a healthier and more sustainable diet. The results showed that all p-values were highly significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating a statistically significant association between dietary change status and all perceived obstacle variables.

To further examine which groups differ significantly, a pairwise Mann–Whitney U test was performed. The analysis compared the three groups: Group 0 (Has Not Changed), Group 1 (Considering Change), and Group 2 (Has Changed). Results indicate that Group 0 perceives significantly greater barriers than the other two groups. Group 1 and Group 2 are more similar in their responses, suggesting that perceived barriers tend to decrease as individuals move from intention to action. While concerns about cost, knowledge, and time constraints lessen, nutritional concerns remain to some extent but tend to decline once individuals have fully transitioned to healthier and more sustainable diets (table 19).

Table 18– Pairwise comparison between perceived Barriers and Dietary Change Status*

	Group 0 vs 1	Group 0 vs 2	Group 1 vs 2	Interpretation
P24.1 (High cost of sustainable food)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	p = 0.0019 (Significant)	0.4867 (Not Significant)	Those who haven't changed their diet (Group 0) perceive cost as a significantly greater barrier than those who have changed (Group 2). Those who haven't changed their diet (Group 0) perceive cost as a significantly greater barrier than those who have changed (Group 2).
P24.2 (Lack of knowledge & information)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	0.4867 (Not Significant)	Those who haven't changed (Group 0) feel much less informed than those considering or who have already changed. Once people start considering dietary change (Group 1), their knowledge gap reduces.
P24.5 (Fear of inadequate nutrition)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	p = 0.0012 (Significant)	p = 0.1267 (Not Significant)	Fear of not getting enough nutrients is much stronger in those who haven't changed their diet. Once people consider or transition, this concern decreases.
P24.7 (Limited availability of fresh products)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	Those who haven't changed (Group 0) feel fresh products are harder to access. This concern drops significantly in Group 1 and 2.
P24.9 (Lack of time for cooking)	p < 0.001 (Highly Significant)	p = 0.0014 (Significant)	p = 0.0316 (Significant)	Time constraints are a major concern in Group 0 but much less in Group 1 or 2. Even Group 1 sees time as a bigger barrier than Group 2, suggesting that meal preparation habits improve after adopting dietary changes.

* Most significant differences Only

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

3.4. Food sustainability awareness and the role of public policies

Participants' perceptions regarding the contribution of their diets to climate change are evenly divided, with 40% believing they contribute and a similar proportion believing they do not—a difference that is not statistically significant. Additionally, 20% of respondents reported uncertainty on the matter.

In contrast, 54% of participants perceive their diet as linked to industrialized food production, particularly in metropolitan areas, with the highest proportion observed in Grande Lisboa (63%). Notably, both age and regional context are significantly associated with this perception of intensive and industrialized agriculture (p < 0.01; see Table 20).

Table 19– Climate change and agriculture intensification awareness

	Contribution to climate change			Diet coming from intensive and industrialized agriculture		
	No	Yes	Don't know	No	Yes	Don't know
Norte	36%	43%	21%	32%	55%	13%
AMP	43%	37%	20%	28%	56%	16%
Centro	40%	41%	19%	38%	46%	16%
OVT	39%	36%	25%	37%	47%	16%
Grande Lisboa (AML)	37%	44%	19%	20%	63%	17%
Península de Setúbal (AML)	45%	34%	21%	25%	56%	19%
Alentejo	36%	36%	27%	30%	48%	22%
Algarve	47%	38%	15%	27%	55%	18%
Portugal (mainland)	40%	40%	20%	29%	54%	16%

Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

Regarding participants' awareness of whether the country is self-sufficient in feeding its population in the context of climate change and global socio-economic instabilities, responses were divided: 43% believe the country is self-sufficient, 39% believe it is not, and 18% are unsure.

Regional differences were minimal, although “No” responses were more prevalent in the Algarve (46%) and the North (43%). This may be linked to the Algarve's vulnerability to drought and water scarcity, and the North's mixed agricultural landscape, which includes both diverse production and areas of agricultural abandonment, particularly in the northeast, where water stress is also a concern. However, this regional variation was not statistically significant.

Figure 22: Perceived National Self-Sufficiency in the Context of Climate Change, by Region
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

When asked whether the government and public policies should support healthier and more sustainable national food production, and encourage healthier and more sustainable individual consumption, the vast majority of respondents (85%) responded affirmatively.

Figure 23: Public policies support for nutritious and sustainable food
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

Participants considered the majority of policy measures to be very important in contributing to the societal transition toward healthier and more sustainable eating habits. Age, gender, and readiness to change dietary behaviors were all statistically significant factors influencing these perceptions ($p < 0.01$).

Figure 24: Perceived Importance of Public Policy Measures Supporting Nutritious and Sustainable eating (Scale: 1 – very important, 5 – not important)
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

Participants generally expressed support for most policy measures; however, the measure "Higher VAT on meat and fish" received the highest frequency of ratings as "not important" (score of 5), which may be linked to cultural preferences and dietary traditions.

To further explore attitudes toward public policy, the relationship between dietary habit changes and opinions on policy measures was analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis H test. Results showed that five variables differed significantly across dietary change groups ($p < 0.05$), indicating that support for certain measures varies depending on individuals' stage of dietary transition.

Pairwise Mann–Whitney U tests revealed that individuals who have already changed their diet (Group 2) or are considering change (Group 1) are more likely to support stronger policy interventions, such as: making fruits and vegetables more affordable, restricting access to unhealthy foods, investing in nutrition education. In contrast, individuals who have not changed their diet (Group 0) tend to rate these measures as less important, suggesting lower support for public intervention. Interestingly, there were no significant differences between those considering change and those who have already changed, implying that support for policy measures strengthens once individuals begin contemplating dietary changes.

Given that food systems directly affect public health, the economy, and the environment, these findings highlight the importance of public policy in supporting the transition to healthier and more sustainable eating habits. They also underscore a broad reliance on state intervention as a driver of systemic change.

Figure 24 highlights the most frequently cited words in the open-ended responses of the survey. Terms such as “sensibilisation” (awareness), “campaigns,” “public policies,” and “price conditions” emerged as the most prominent, reflecting participants’ emphasis on the importance of education, state action, and economic accessibility in promoting healthier and more sustainable diets.

Figure 25: most frequently cited words in open-questions about suggestions.
(image generated in <https://www.wordclouds.com/>)
Source: Care4Food, 2025; GfK, 2024

4. EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS OF PATTERNS AND DETERMINANTS OF FOOD CHOICES FOR FOOD SECURITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

The survey analysis indicates that multiple factors influence changes in food choices, highlighting the importance of understanding these interrelated drivers to design effective interventions that promote healthier and more sustainable dietary habits.

Socio-political, economic, and food environment factors act as external drivers of change, alongside influences at the individual and interpersonal levels (Swinburn et al., 2011; Sobal et al., 2014). Drawing on the socio-ecological framework and the Behaviour Change Wheel (see Section 1.2), we identified variables aligned with the Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation (COM-B) model that can inform the analysis (Table 20).

Table 20 - Overview of indicators by phase, framework, and data source used in cluster formation and in exploratory analysis

Phase	Variables	SEM/FAO	COM_B	Classification	Data source
1	Cluster	Environmental context / drivers	Physical and social opportunity	Cluster: Rural - 1; Semi-urban - 2; Economic specialized and multicultural - 3; Urban - 4	
1	OF_HORTICULTURE	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Presence of horticultural agriculture	INE, Agriculture census, 2019
1	OF_DENS_POP_2021	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Population density	INE, Population census, 2021
1	OS_FOREIGN_2021	Social context	Social opportunity	Proportion of foreign population	INE, Population census, 2021
1	OF_WATER	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Water usage in agriculture and households per capita	INE, Stats yearbook 2021-2023
1	OF_STORES_CAPITAL	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Food stores within 5 min walk per 10,000 inhabitants	OSM, EEA, CLC 2024, own calculations
1	OF_PRCPOP_DESERTS	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Areas classified as food deserts	OSM, EEA, CLC 2024, own calculations
1	OF_AGRIFAM	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Presence of small-scale agricultural supply chains	INE, Agriculture census, 2019
1	OS_OLDER_65	Social context	Social opportunity	Ageing rate of the population	INE, Population census, 2021
1	OS_UNEMPLOY	Social context	Social opportunity	Unemployment rate	INE, Population census, 2021
1	OF_CAR	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Proportion of the population using cars for commuting	INE, Population census, 2021
1	OS_EDUCATION	Social context	Social opportunity	Educational levels of the population	INE, Population census, 2021
1	OF_INCOME	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Average income level	INE, Population census, 2021
1	OF_EXPORTS	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Export coverage rate	INE, Stats yearbook 2021-2023
1	OF_INVESTMENT_MUNICIPAL	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Government investments in biodiversity conservation	INE, Stats yearbook 2021-2023

1	OF_TECH_MUNICIPAL	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Use of technologies in the government sector	INE, Stats yearbook 2021-2023
1	OF_TECH_POP	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Proportion of population using digital technologies	INE, Stats yearbook 2021-2023
1	OF_VARPOP	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Variation in population size over time	Population census, 2021
2	MR_CHANGE_HABITS (dependent Z)	Individual	Reflexive motivation	Has changed toward sustainable consumption: 1 = Yes; 0 = No	survey, 2024
2	CPP_GENDER	Individual Social	Psychological capacity / Physical	Gender of the respondent: 1 = Male; 2 = Female; 0 = Non-binary; 3 = Prefer not to answer	survey, 2024
2	CPP_AGE	Individual	Psychological / Physical capacity	Age of the respondent	survey, 2024
2	OS_ADULTS	Social context	Social opportunity	Number of adults in the household	survey, 2024
2	OS_CHILDREN	Social context	Social opportunity	Number of children in the household	survey, 2024
2	CF_PROFESSION	Individual	Physical capacity	Professional status: 1 = Retired; 2 = Employed; 3 = Student; 4 = Unemployed; 5 = Domestic work	survey, 2024
2	MR_INSECURITY_FAO	Individual	Reflexive motivation	Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) – FAO food security index: 0 = secure; 1 = Moderately insecure (or at risk); 3 severely insecure	survey, 2024
2	CF_COOKING	Individual	Physical capacity	Main person responsible for cooking: 1 = Respondent; 2 = Spouse; 3 = Shared; 4 = Other; 5 = No one cooks	survey, 2024
2	CF_SHOPPING	Individual	Physical capacity	Main person responsible for shopping: 1 = Respondent; 2 = Spouse; 3 = Shared; 4 = Other; 5 = No one shops	survey, 2024
2	OF_DISTANCE	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Time to walk to nearest fresh food store: 1 = 5 minutes; 2 = 10 minutes; 3 = 15 minutes or more	survey, 2024
2	OF_DIVERSITY	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Is there a diversity of fresh food available within a 5-minute walk? 1 = Yes; 2 = No	survey, 2024
2	CP_CLIMATECHANGE	Individual	Psychological capacity	Awareness of climate change: 2 = Yes; 1 = No; 0 = Don't know	survey, 2024
2	CP_AGRICULTURE	Individual	Psychological capacity	Awareness of intensive agriculture issues: 2 = Yes; 1 = No; 0 = Don't know	survey, 2024
2	OF_P24_PRICE_OF_FOOD	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Price of food as a barrier to changing habits (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024
2	CP_FOOD_LACK_KNOWLEDGE	Individual	Psychological capacity	Lack of knowledge as a barrier (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024
2	MA_STRESS	Individual	Automatic motivation	Stress as a barrier (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024
2	OS_NORMS_VALUES	Social context	Social opportunity	Cultural and social norms as a barrier (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024
2	MR_FEAR_ADEQUATE_NUTRITION	Individual	Reflexive motivation	Fear of inadequate nutrition as a barrier (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024
2	OF_OFFER_OF_FOOD	Environmental context	Physical opportunity	Lack of fresh food availability as a barrier (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024
2	MR_LACK_OF_TASTE	Individual	Reflexive motivation	Lack of taste or cooking skills as a barrier (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024

2	CF_LACK_OF_TIME	Individual	Physical capacity	Lack of time to cook as a barrier (1 = Very important to 5 = Not important)	survey, 2024
2	CP_AUTOSUFFICIENCY	Individual	Psychological capacity	Awareness of self-sufficiency: 2 = Yes; 1 = No; 0 = Don't know	survey, 2024
2	OS_STATE_INTERVENTION	Social context	Social opportunity	Belief in the need for state intervention: 2 = Yes; 1 = No; 0 = Don't know	survey, 2024
2	CP_BMI	Individual	Physical capacity	Body Mass Index (BMI)	survey, 2024
2	CP_EDUCATION	Individual	Psychological capacity	Education level: 0 = Illiterate; 1 = Primary; 2 = Basic School; 3 = High School; 4 = Graduate; 5 = Doctorate	survey, 2024
2	CF_DISEASES	Individual	Physical capacity	Presence of chronic disease: 1 = Yes; 0 = No	survey, 2024
2	MR_DIET_PERCEPTION	Individual	Reflexive motivation	Self-perceived diet quality: 5 = Very good to 1 = Very poor	survey, 2024

A two-step exploratory analysis was conducted. First, environmental and social context variables were used (see table 20 column - step) to identify types of regions. Secondly, individual context variables were used to analyze what best predicts behavioral changes. In this second stage, sustainable diet score and habits change are the variables that were more likely to be used as dependent variables.

4.1. Cluster Analysis of the Food and Contextual Environment in Portuguese NUTS III Regions

In this analysis we aimed to identify types of territories (regions NUTSIII) based on variables reflecting the food environment (demographic, socioeconomic, and infrastructural factors) and the social context. That is a set of Indicators were selected to reflect dimensions such as:

- Food environment and Infrastructure: fast food availability, proximity to retail, horticulture production, car ownership, water consumption.

- Socioeconomic and demographic context: unemployment, purchasing power, education, urban pressure, foreign population, aging index

All variables were standardized (z-scores) to ensure comparability across regions. K-Means clustering was applied using Euclidean distance. The Elbow method and silhouette scores supported choosing 4 clusters:

- *Cluster 1: Rural and Aging Context*

Low access to food stores, low fast food and car ownership. High aging index, lower education, and purchasing power. Indicates a low-access, low-choice food environment, possibly at risk of food insecurity among older populations.

- *Cluster 2: Agricultural and multicultural Area*

High water use, foreign population, high agricultural exports and accessible food environment. Moderate socioeconomic indicators and lower urban pressure. Represents a semi-rural and specialized environment.

- *Cluster 3: Transitional/Developing*

Mixed profile with some urban traits and moderate scores across most indicators. May represent semi-urban or periurban environment.

- *Cluster 4: Urban, Diverse & Consumer-Oriented*

High densities of stores where it is possible to access fast and ultra-processed food, proximity to fresh food stores, higher levels of foreign population, purchasing power, young population and education. Strong infrastructure (internet, water access). Reflects a high-access, high-choice food environment typical of metropolitan areas.

Analyzing these regions through the lens of the COM-B model allows us to infer how regional differences may shape sustainable and secure food behaviors. In this model, Opportunity refers to environmental and social-structural factors that either enable or constrain food behavior at a broader level. Proximity to food stores, car ownership, and the quality of urban infrastructure serve as useful proxies for physical opportunity.

Clusters 2, 3, and 4 benefit from more favorable opportunity structures, while Cluster 1 faces more significant limitations. These opportunities are closely interlinked with Capability and Motivation. For instance, environments characterized by higher educational levels or a more diverse, younger population may enhance capability and foster motivational factors such as habits, norms, and cultural openness toward sustainable food behaviors.

Clusters 2 and 4 exhibit the strongest motivational potential, driven by economic vitality and cultural diversity. In contrast, Cluster 1 may encounter motivational barriers, largely due to an aging population and more static social structures. The regional clusters reflect observed or inferred food-related behaviors, shaped by varying levels of food accessibility, infrastructure, and socioeconomic and cultural conditions. These behaviors influence both individual food choices and broader outcomes such as food sustainability and food security. Notably, Cluster 3 appears most vulnerable, potentially lacking both opportunity and capability. On the other hand, Cluster 1 aligns with high-choice, high-consumption environments, which present different kinds of challenges for sustainable food behavior.

This clustering approach provides a valuable framework for contextualizing territorial differences and guiding region-specific strategies in public health, food policy, and spatial planning.

Figure 26: NUTS III Clusters
Source: Care4Food

Figure 27: Cluster and variables B-plots
Source: Care4Food

4.2 Individual-Level Food Behavioural changes

To complement the contextual analysis, an individual-level behavioral model was developed using a binary logistic regression applied to the full national sample and subsequently disaggregated by Clusters 1, 2, 3, and 4. The model estimated the probability of reported changes in food habits as a function of selected predictors. The dependent variable, **MR_CHANGE_HABITS**, was a binary indicator denoting whether respondents reported a shift toward more sustainable food practices (1 = Yes; 0 = No).

To preserve statistical power and avoid listwise deletion, “Don’t know” responses were not treated as missing values but were instead recoded into dummy variables and retained as valid categories. This approach recognizes that non-response may capture meaningful constructs (e.g., uncertainty or low awareness) and allows for a more inclusive estimation of behavioral predictors. All predictors exhibited acceptable multicollinearity levels, with Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) below 2—well within conventional thresholds (typically VIF < 5 or 7).

The general model was estimated using a nationally representative sample of 1,170 individuals, comprising 599 respondents who reported no change and 571 who reported a change. Analyses were conducted in **SPSS (version 28)**. Following preliminary testing, the final model was estimated using the **stepwise forward conditional method**, which sequentially introduces predictors based on their statistical significance. Key configuration parameters included a significance level of 0.05 for entry, 0.10 for removal, and a classification cut-off of 0.50 for predicted probabilities. Model diagnostics assessed overall fit, classification accuracy, and residual patterns.

The logistic regression model follows the standard form (1)

$$\log\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_k X_k$$

where P is the probability of reporting a change in food habits, β_0 is the intercept, and β_1 through β_k are the estimated coefficients for each predictor variable X_1 through X_k

The predicted probabilities can be obtained by transforming the logit score Z using the logistic function of equation (2):

(2)

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-Z}}$$

The national-level logistic regression model was statistically significant at step 11, $\chi^2(11) = 236.108$, $p < .001$, explaining approximately 24.4% of the variance in the outcome variable (Nagelkerke $R^2 = .244$). The Hosmer–Lemeshow test indicated a good model fit ($\chi^2 = 4.649$, $df = 8$, $p = .794$). The model achieved an overall classification accuracy of 69.0%, correctly predicting 68.4% of cases with no behavioral change and 69.7% of cases reporting a change.

Model performance was further evaluated using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. The area under the curve (AUC) was 0.748 (SE = 0.014, 95% CI [0.720, 0.775]), indicating good discriminative ability. This suggests that the model correctly distinguishes between individuals who changed their behavior and those who did not approximately 74.8% of the time. The result was statistically significant ($p < .001$), confirming that the model performs significantly better than chance.

Of the 26 predictors included in the initial model, 11 were statistically significant ($p < .05$) at the national level. When disaggregated by food environment clusters, the number of significant predictors varied: 4 for Cluster 1, 8 for Cluster 2, 3 for Cluster 3, and 11 for Cluster 4 (see Table 21).

Table 21 - Logistic Regression Coefficients (B) and Odds Ratios (Exp(B)) for General Model and Clusters 1–4 of Dietary Change (MR_CHANGE)

Z	Variable code	General model		Cluster 1		Cluster 2		cluster 3		cluster 4	
		B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)
x1	CPP_GENDER	0.368	1.445			0.714	2.042				
x3	CP_CLIMATECHANGE	1.008	2.739							1.074	2.926
x5	OF_PRICE OF FOOD							-0.848	0.428	-0.176	0.839
x6	CP_LACK_KNOWLEDGE	-0.18	0.835			-0.262	0.769			-0.139	0.87
x8	OS_NORMS_VALUES					-0.307	0.735				
x9	MR_FEAR INADEQUATE_NUTRITION	-0.227	0.797							-0.232	0.793
x10	OF_OFFER OF FOOD			-0.402	0.669						
x11	MR_LACK_OF_TASTE					0.276	1.318				
x15	OS_STATE	0.423	1.526							0.404	1.497
x16	CP_BMI									-0.056	0.945
x17	CP_EDUCATION	0.326	1.385	0.541	1.717	0.376	1.457	1.118	3.058	0.229	1.257
x19	MR_DIET_PERCEPTION	0.308	1.36			0.361	1.435			0.267	1.306
x23	MR_INSECURITY_FAO					0.516	1.676				
x24	CF_COOKING			-0.391	0.677						
x26	OF_DISTANCE	0.206	1.229								
Dummy (don't know answers)	CP_CLIMATECHANGE	1.206	3.339								0.026
	MR_FEAR INADEQUATE_NUTRITION	-1.618	0.198					-21.03	0		0.004
	MR_LACK_OF_TASTE	-0.999	0.368								
	OS_NORMS_VALUES			-21.053	0	-1.411	0.244				
	CF_LACK_OF_TIME									-20.693	0

Some statistically significant predictors were consistent with theoretical expectations, such as gender, education level, and perceived diet quality, thereby reinforcing the validity of the analytical framework. In contrast, variables including age, employment status, and household composition did not emerge as significant in the general model.

When linking individual behavior change to regional clusters, preliminary exploration suggests:

- Ageing regions (Cluster 1) demonstrate lower change intention, consistent with barriers such as low education and strong ingrained habits.

- Agricultural and multicultural regions (Cluster 2) exhibit mixed responses, maybe influenced by habits and food preferences. This Cluster offers strong potential for developing short food supply chains and fostering local food resilience.

- Transitional areas (Cluster 3) fall in between, showing variability that may reflect evolving infrastructure and awareness. These regions should be prioritized for infrastructure improvements and proactive food environment planning

- Urban/affluent regions (Cluster 4) show higher proportions of individuals intending to change behavior, possibly due to higher education and label awareness. Urban clusters (Cluster 4) may require policies promoting healthy food choices and urban design that mitigate overexposure to ultra-processed foods.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study aimed to provide an in-depth understanding of food choices and perceptions among the population of mainland Portugal, analyzed at both regional and individual levels.

In addition to the collection of secondary indicators (such as statistics and land use data), a comprehensive survey of 1,813 individuals was conducted. This allowed the identification of territorial patterns and individual drivers of dietary change toward more sustainable food behaviors. The study employed a combined socio-ecological and behavioral framework (SEM and COM-B) to examine how individual and environmental factors influence food behavior, with the additional goal of informing public policy and supporting systemic changes in food systems.

This study confirms that dietary behavior change toward sustainability is not merely a matter of individual choice, but the result of complex, interacting factors spanning biological, psychological, environmental, social, and territorial dimensions. In line with socio-ecological models (Story et al., 2008; HLPE, 2017), our findings show that personal capability and motivation are deeply influenced by contextual opportunity structures. These insights are especially relevant in the context of ongoing global efforts to transform food systems in alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals and European policy frameworks.

5.1. Main limitations

This study also faced some limitations. They are related with the sample itself. Although quota sampling ensured demographic balance across age, gender, and region, certain vulnerable or at-risk groups may still be underrepresented—such as undocumented migrants or individuals living in extreme poverty or in food deserts. These populations are often more severely food insecure and face more complex barriers to adopting sustainable eating habits, potentially skewing the results toward more favorable averages.

The study also relies heavily on self-reported data, including dietary habits, health status (e.g., self-reported weight and height for BMI), and perceptions of sustainable practices. While this approach is practical and cost-effective, it introduces potential biases, such as recall bias and social desirability bias. Participants may overstate the healthiness or sustainability of their diets, particularly when these behaviors are viewed as socially desirable. This tendency is reflected in the weak correlation (Pearson = 0.23) between perceived and actual sustainable food practices. To address this, a sustainable diet score was calculated to better assess real behaviors.

Another limitation involves the measurement of food insecurity. The study employed only 3 of the 8 standard questions from the FAO's Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES), which reduces the capacity to capture the full spectrum of food insecurity experiences. The full FIES is designed to assess not only food access, but also the psychological and behavioral impacts of food insecurity. As such, using a shortened version may have underestimated moderate or severe food insecurity, or failed to reflect coping strategies. To compensate, a composite food security

indicator was developed, incorporating variables such as the presence of children, employment status, income level, and food expenses.

Furthermore, the study is cross-sectional, offering a snapshot in time. While this design is suitable for identifying associations and describing current behaviors, it does not support causal inference. For instance, although the analysis shows a relationship between high BMI and chronic disease, it cannot determine whether poor dietary habits caused obesity, or if pre-existing health conditions influenced eating behaviors. Longitudinal studies would be required to clarify such causal relationships.

Lastly, caution is needed when interpreting regional data. While the study aggregates results at the NUTS III level to allow for regional comparison, the sampling frame was designed at the NUTS II level. As a result, intra-regional disparities—particularly in larger or more heterogeneous regions—may be obscured. Interpretations at the sub-regional level should therefore be approached with care, recognizing potential sampling limitations and variability within regions.

5.2. Results in the broader conceptual framework

At the regional level, the data highlight that mainland Portugal is far from homogeneous. Clear distinctions emerge between coastal and inland areas, with metropolitan regions showing different dynamics compared to aging, low-density interior regions. Certain territories—such as Alentejo Litoral and Algarve—stand out due to the influence of tourism, agriculture, and multiculturalism, while rural-urban transition zones show increasing levels of accessibility, albeit still heavily reliant on car use.

At the individual level, the results reveal diverse perceptions and behaviors:

- 13% of Portuguese households face moderate to severe food insecurity, with the highest rates in the Algarve region.
- 66% of diets are rich in meat and dairy, and 3% of the participants follow vegetarian or vegan diets. Algarve report following a mediterranean diet (39% against 31% national average)
- Only 22% chose highly sustainable meals when presented with several options—showing a significant gap between knowledge and action, even among those who identify with sustainable dietary practices.
- The average food sustainability score is 3 out of 5, placing 52% of the population above average. 12% of the sample as a score above 2. Coimbra Region as the higher average score. In contrast the perception of having a sustainable diet with overrated as 81% believe following and sustainable and healthy diet.
- 32% have changed their eating habits, mainly reducing red meat; 33% are considering changes and 35% do not consider change rating barriers like cost and knowledge has perceived obstacles.
- People who changed their diet have changed because of health issues (61%)
- 40% believe their diet has impact on climate change, but the other 40% don't believe in that impact
- Cooking responsibilities remain gendered, with 70% of women reporting primary responsibility versus 32% of men.

- Most participants are satisfied with their access to fresh products within a 5-minute walk from home (69%), but 63% of participants use a private car for food shopping, highlighting reliance on non-sustainable transport in many regions.
- 85% support stronger government action, specially making fruits and vegetables more affordable and accessible, support nutrition education and public awareness campaigns

Then, a comprehensive analysis of regions and individuals was explored with machine learning and cluster analysis identified territorial patterns influencing food behaviors, showing that both individual and regional factors like urbanization, income, and access, can have influence on dietary practices and readiness to change. The five most influential individual variables of driving behavioral change were: Lack of taste in healthy food, Cultural habits, norms and values, habits, difficulties in understanding food labels, Lack of time, Educational level, sustainability awareness and in a small portion age and gender. When linking individual behavior change to regional clusters, preliminary exploration suggests: Ageing regions (Cluster 1) demonstrate lower change intention. Agricultural and multicultural regions (Cluster 2) exhibit mixed responses, maybe influenced by habits and food preferences. Transitional rural to urban areas (Cluster 3) fall in between, showing variability that may reflect evolving infrastructure and awareness. Urban regions (Cluster 4) show higher proportions of individuals intending to change behavior, possibly due to higher education and label awareness.

Figure 28 highlights main drivers towards sustainable food habits change. Although all the components of the COM-B are represented, most of them reflect psychological capacities and physical opportunities acting as barriers or as enablers (also see figure 6 – conceptual framework). The results may suggest that public policy interventions not only should target Groups differently, but also territories.

Figure 28 – main drivers of food habits change towards sustainability.

Therefore, what are the most effective ways to engage individuals and territories in long-term food sustainability and climate change resilience?

5.3. Policy Implications and Future Directions

When it comes to individuals, targeted strategies are essential. Groups that are not considering dietary change may require additional interventions focused on education, food literacy, and behavioral support. These should include affordable food options, practical cooking guidance, and culturally sensitive approaches. Crucially, these efforts must be linked with national food, health, and sustainability programs, reinforcing the idea that food literacy goes beyond nutrition—it must also encompass sustainability, equity, and environmental responsibility. The concept of sustainable diets is not exclusive to vulnerable populations; it is a universal issue.

Although vulnerable groups are disproportionately affected by food insecurity, the data show that overweight, unhealthy eating patterns, and unsustainable diets are widespread across all demographics. Therefore, a universal policy approach is needed—one that not only addresses the needs of disadvantaged populations but also drives systemic and structural changes in food environments.

In terms of opportunities, the study highlights the value of local food circuits, proximity-based shopping (e.g., walking to fresh food outlets), and the role of availability and accessibility of fresh products. These findings emphasize that agriculture must be viewed not only as subsistence or local production, but as a key element in fostering climate resilience, food sovereignty, and public health. Accordingly, public policies on food should fully integrate agroecology and regenerative agriculture as foundational pillars of territorial and urban sustainability strategies.

5.4. Building a National Food Sustainability Observatory

One of the key recommendations is the creation of a Food Sustainability Observatory. The study's robust database—combined with tools such as real-time dashboards, citizen science features, and periodic surveys—offers an opportunity to establish a scalable monitoring system, down to the municipal level. This observatory would support evidence-based policymaking, foster civic participation, and enhance accountability and transparency in the transformation of food systems.

At present, the Care4Food dashboard and story maps serve as dynamic, visual tools that allow both policymakers and the public to explore regional disparities and behavioral trends. However, the ambition is to evolve this into an interactive, participatory platform where individuals can not only track their personal food sustainability scores, but also understand the aggregate impact of their diets at the local level—contributing to a shared vision of sustainable communities.

Figure 29 – The Care4Food Dashboard.

Source: Care4Food, 2025; from GfK, 2024, INE and DGT 2024

Available at <https://www.arcgis.com/apps/dashboards/9088fa801b454f32afa39d5c84e10c7b>

Código de campo alterado

The CARE4FOOD dashboard presents indicators of food environment and sustainable food consumption in Portugal, including maps of store density and municipal sustainable food scores. The fresh food store density and the fast food score densities indicators were built using OSM data, considering supermarkets, markets, grocery stores, and also fast food and convenience stores, applying a kernel density with a 500 m radius (proximity representation of a 5-minute walking distance, extendable to 15 minutes) and excluding non-residential areas, from land use.

The municipal sustainable food score, aggregates individual food scores by municipality and it is interactive, meaning that when a participant fulfills a survey the score is updated by municipality

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